

Bio-Cultural Rights of Indigenous Peoples in India: An Analysis

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Aneesha

Research Scholar &
Faculty
Department Of Laws
Panjab University
Chandigarh, Punjab, India

Abstract

Bio-cultural rights are the multi-dimensional rights incorporating wide aspects ranging from the human rights to the rights relating to self-governance. The conversation in regard to indigenous peoples and their concerns started in 2007 with the coming of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of the Indigenous Peoples. The present research paper is about the **various rights** of indigenous peoples in India. The paper discusses the **term "indigenous peoples" and the "bio-cultural rights"**. It also focuses on the **historical background** of the development of the legal regime with regard to the rights conferred upon these communities who have faced discrimination at the hands of the state itself along with private entities since ancient times. The paper also studies the **legislation** involved in the matters connected with the rights of the indigenous peoples and the recourse available to them under the said enforced laws. It also analyses the **constitutional safeguards** enacted for the protection and welfare of the indigenous peoples by conferring on some of them the status of Schedule Tribes.

Keywords

Indigenous peoples, Bio-Cultural Rights, Scheduled Tribes, Forest Rights Act, Fifth Schedule, Scheduled Areas, Self-governance, Panchayats, etc.

Introduction

Economic development leads to the overall development or upliftment of any society, but this does not mean that all sections of society which are quite different from each other will also progress along equally as a result of it. Taking the case of the indigenous population of any region, economic development ironically leads to the destruction of the livelihoods of many in this section of society. Indigenous peoples stand on a different footing than the others as this community is largely dependent on the natural resources in the environment. Due to this, the changes brought by economic development are usually unfavourable for them, as their resources in the form of land and forests get depleted or acquired by other parties- be it at the hands of private parties or the state, leaving them in dark or even if in lieu of it compensation is provided, it is obviously insufficient for this compensation is a temporary relief or a short-term one for uprooting their livelihoods permanently. This violation of their essential human rights, by market such as multi-national corporations (MNCs) and big corporate players along with the state, is also not addressed by ordinary legislations. Thus, this scenario continued over a long period of time, giving birth to everlasting historical land disputes and disputes regarding the ownership of natural resources, found on those lands. These disputes continued to linger on for years and years, thus reaching nowhere, but endangering the subsistence of indigenous communities making them a vulnerable section of the society we live in, and slowly isolating them and encroaching upon their inherent rights. Finally, mankind realized the historical discrimination meted out to the indigenous community, and an international effort commenced towards the acknowledgment and recognition of their rights, ultimately achieving a significant milestone in the form of the widely acclaimed United Nations Declaration on The Rights of Indigenous Peoples, 2007 [2] (UNDRIP).

Objective of study

The present paper will analyze the rights of the indigenous peoples, the struggle behind their acknowledgment by the global community, the national legislative framework regarding indigenous peoples, the international instruments dealing with the present issue, and other connected issues.

Review of Literature

'Indigenous peoples' term is used for a certain type of community that identifies itself differently from the rest of the population residing in that particular area or region. Indigenous communities cannot be defined by fixed phrases or terms but these are to be identified through some distinctive traits like- distinct culture, language, way of living, traditional means of livelihood, system of self-governance usually suffering from decades of subjugation and discrimination at the hands of the state by encroaching upon their proprietary and human rights through dispossessing them from their lands which are the prized possessions of this community, adversely affecting their socio-cultural fabric. Since this community is so diverse, it's diversity varies from region to region, thus, it has been thought better not to define them in any words, as that would limit or restrict the scope of legislations or instruments applicable to the set of population having basic characteristics of 'indigenous peoples' but not meeting the strict criteria which would have been laid down by the definition if it were given any. Along with this, an important criterion of any community to be recognized as an 'indigenous community' is that that particular community must identify itself to be so. A most suitable and accepted definition of 'indigenous peoples' has been given by Martinez Cobo in his study on the indigenous communities - "Indigenous communities, peoples and nations are those which, having a historical continuity with pre-invasion and pre-colonial societies that developed on their

territories, consider themselves distinct from other sectors of the societies now prevailing on those territories, or parts of them. They form at present non-dominant sectors of society and are determined to preserve, develop and transmit to future generations their ancestral territories, and their ethnic identity, as the basis of their continued existence as peoples, in accordance with their own cultural patterns, social institutions and legal system.” [3]The first international instrument dealing with indigenous peoples- International Labour Organisation (ILO) Convention No. 169 also laid down a criteria for defining ‘indigenous peoples’ viz. “peoples in independent countries who are regarded as indigenous on account of their descent from the populations which inhabited the country, or a geographical region to which the country belongs, at the time of conquest or colonisation or the establishment of present state boundaries and who, irrespective of their legal status, retain some or all of their own social, economic, cultural and political institutions.” Also,[4] in addition to the above criteria, at the same time, it also states that the fundamental criterion for a tribal or indigenous is that they recognize themselves to be such.[5] Another definition has been phrased by the Expert Mechanism carefully, not restricting the scope of the term ‘indigenous culture’. “Indigenous peoples’ cultures include tangible and intangible manifestations of their ways of life, achievements and creativity, are an expression of their self-determination and of their spiritual and physical relationships with their lands, territories and resources. Indigenous cultures is a holistic concept based on common material and spiritual values and includes distinctive manifestations in language, spirituality, membership, arts, literature, traditional knowledge, customs, rituals, ceremonies, methods of production, festive events, music, sports and traditional games, behaviour, habits, tools, shelter, clothing, economic activities, morals, value systems, cosmovisions, laws, and activities such as hunting, fishing, trapping and gathering.”[6] Further, the term ‘indigenous peoples’ itself is not used universally over the world.[7] Various phrases are used in vernacular language of many regions which are used to address a particular community having same or similar traits as indigenous communities like- “Alaska Native”, “aboriginal”, “First Nations”, “Adivasis”, “Janjati”, “hill people”, “hunter-gatherers” etc. Thus, indigeneity amongst the communities cannot be defined but only can be recognized or identified.

Since the present paper is about the bio-cultural rights of indigenous peoples, there is a need to interpret the meaning of this term and what is included under “bio-cultural rights”. Bio-cultural rights is a collective term for a number of rights like the right to land, culture, protection of traditional knowledge, conservation and management of bio-diversity in their territories etc. These set of rights are based on the interlink between the environment and the culture.[8] This implies that bio-cultural rights in the context of indigenous peoples are the rights related to their land, the natural resources located on them, and the bio-diversity including the variety of plants, animals, micro-organisms etc. found on that land. This relationship between the environment and culture which is fundamental to these rights is generally of a caretaker or a protector, which is a form of symbiotic relationship. With varying indigenous communities, these rights vary ostensibly, but fundamentally, these are based upon this mutual relationship discussed above. The world, being based on the capitalistic view, always observes these resources as something to exploit for materialistic gains, land becomes more of a tradable commodity rather than a natural resource. This difference in the two approaches is what has kept the issue of ‘bio-cultural rights’ away from recognition in international law.[9]

Main Text

Historical Background

As seen above, the adverse effects were observed due to the approach followed by the world community towards natural resources. These adverse effects were seen in the form of environmental degradation, consequently harming the communities surviving on them solely and working for the protection of these resources. The changes in the ownership of these resources from these local communities to the state agencies resulted in the destruction of the ecology rather than its conservation. Thus, it was realized that the said approach was an overall failure. The recognition of bio-cultural rights would be a better alternative leading to a win-win situation, conserving the environment on the one hand and protecting the local communities on the other hand.[10] These rights emerged as community rights i.e. belonging to a certain group i.e. the rights are given as a person is a member of a certain group unlike the first-generation rights, which contain certain civil and political guarantees, which are largely individual rights. If the said person ceases to be a member of the group, the rights will also vanish. Also, these rights owe their existence to the ancient relationship between the right holder’s community and their environment. On the international front, the movement, so to say, for the rights of indigenous peoples began in 1923, with a hearing on the right of the tribals for self-governance at the League of Nations. But it was in the 1980s that some success was achieved officially in the shape of formation of the Working Group on Indigenous Populations (WGIP) as a result of consistent efforts of indigenous communities who represented their issues before the United Nations (UN). Time and again, the right to self-determination was stressed by the indigenous peoples in their struggle. With the coming of the Convention on Biological Diversity in 1993, this right of self-determination saw addition of newer aspects into it, leading to the growth in its ambit. Various other international agreements and treaties have concurred with this approach. The indigenous communities have presented shreds of evidence of the direct link between their rights and the conservation of environment due to a unique cultural and spiritual relationship with their ecological home. In 1999, an entire set of articles on the significance of bio-diversity were published, whose editor Darrell Addison Posey initiated other

anthropologists working in this field to investigate the connection between the contribution of indigenous communities and the conservation of biological diversity. Posey can thus be named as the crusader of bio-cultural rights as he was the first to advocate the importance of this set of rights for the conservation of environment. This set of rights was named as 'Traditional Resource Rights' (TRR).[11] Thus, the bio-cultural rights emerged from the need to protect and conserve the environment which was not fulfilled by the initial approach which had the state as the controlling agency of the natural resources which originally belong to the indigenous communities who share a unique bond with them.

Indian Legislations On Indigenous Peoples

About 104 million Indians belong to the indigenous community some of whom have also been recognized as 'Scheduled Tribes' under the Constitution giving [12] them special benefits and protection. There are several legislations and constitutional provisions that protect the rights and promote the welfare of indigenous peoples. Unlike most of the nations, India has given constitutional recognition to some of its indigenous communities by conferring on them the status of 'Scheduled Tribes'. This conferring of status changes the scenario altogether, as each provision of the constitution is sacrosanct. Many articles of the constitution contain special provisions for tribal communities like articles 15, 16 and 19 contained in Part III, which lists the most important provisions i.e. the fundamental rights. The constitution does not discriminate in any way when guaranteeing these rights to the tribals rather, there are certain positive discriminations being made by the constitution in favour of the tribal population in matters of education and employment specifically. Various special programmes have also been launched by the government for the health and overall well-being of the tribal community. Article 19(5) even restricts the fundamental right of the rest of the citizens, for safeguarding the interests of the indigenous community [13] Article 244(1) provides for the administration and control of scheduled areas and scheduled tribes, ensuring the protection of their culture, customs, and land rights. The constitution also establishes the National Commission for Scheduled Tribes, which is responsible for safeguarding the rights and interests of scheduled tribes in India. The commission, established by Article 338A, oversees the welfare of the schedule tribes. It protects the community from exploitation or discrimination of any kind, ensuring the upliftment of the community in general. A brief historical background of the commission, it was setup in 1978 through a resolution of Ministry of Home Affairs. It got constitutional status in 1990 vide 65th Amendment Act. Under this amendment, the commission for Schedule Tribes and Schedule Castes was a single body. Further, in 2003 constitution was again amended by 89th Amendment Act, modifying article 338 and separating the two commissions for Schedule Tribes and Schedule Castes respectively. Finally, it stands as a distinct constitutional body as per art.338A in present. It is a supervising, monitoring and an advisory body which examines and evaluates the existing protective and welfare measures of the government and various schemes under the Constitution itself or any other law, implemented for the Schedule Tribes. It also advises on the matters involving future policies, programmes and initiatives required to be undertaken by the government for the socio-economic progress of the community. It also presents a report to the President upon the effectiveness of the said policies, programmes and initiatives etc. The service conditions and the tenure of the members of the commission ensure that the members of this community are represented along with the women. The commission has investigatory powers and can inquire into any matter involving the rights of Schedule Tribes. The commission is equivalent to a civil court while conducting an inquiry. In addition to the functions given in art.338A of the Constitution, the commission has been assigned certain tasks like- identifying and recommending measures which need to be adopted for the welfare of the ST_s who are residing in forest areas and their right to ownership over minor forest produce, minerals, water resources etc, resettlement of displaced tribes in the course of developmental constructions etc.[14] Apart from these key articles, there are Schedules Fifth and Sixth appended to the Constitution which protect the tribal areas and classify some of the tribal areas as the Scheduled Areas. The aim of these schedules " is not only to prevent acquisition, holding or disposal of the land in Scheduled Areas by the non-tribals from the tribals or alienation of such land among non-tribals inter se but also to ensure that the tribals remain in possession and enjoyment of the lands in Scheduled Areas for their economic empowerment, social status and [the] dignity of their person. Equally exploitation of mineral resources [for] national wealth undoubtedly, is for the development of the nation." [15]

Besides the above constitutional provisions, there are some key legislations enacted by the Parliament for the welfare of the ST_s of which the foremost is the **Scheduled Tribes and Other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Recognition of Forest Rights) Act, 2006**, also known as the Forest Rights Act (FRA). The Act is a part of reformation of forest governance, which recognized the state led discrimination and neglect of forest dwelling communities. It also recognizes the rights of the community at both levels viz. individual as well as community level. While the right to habitation and self-cultivation are usually regarded as individual rights, grazing, fishing and access to forest water resources, traditional knowledge, biodiversity are recognized as community rights.[16] A detailed list of rights has been given under Section 3 of the Act. The Act aims to reverse the injustice continuing since a long period against the tribals and forest dwellers by acknowledging their rights over the forests in various forms, and also it attempts to bring

forward these communities by entrusting them the right as well as the role of a guardian to their ancient lands, thus, reinforcing the ancient and sacred relation between them. The scope of the Act is very wide as besides Scheduled Tribes, the rest of the community who live in the forests although not recognized as Scheduled Tribes are also covered here. It introduces the institution of tribal councils in the role of managers of forests, forest conservation and wildlife conservation.[17] It attempts to recognize certain set of pre-existing rights in context of forest lands, along with establishing the Gram Sabhas as the authority to exercise these rights over their traditional territories. Further, the Act also incorporates the free, prior and informed consent regime in consonance with the various international conventions. The Act is a landmark piece of legislation as it affirms the view that local tribal communities actually perform the role of a guardian towards their environment, thus conserving the very forest lands they live and depend upon.[18] This approach of the Act is in line with the bio-cultural rights approach.

The **Panchayats (Extension to Scheduled Areas) Act, 1996** is another important legislation dealing with the tribal people. As the name suggests, it extends the provisions of the Panchayati Raj system which was established by 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act, 1992 to the Fifth Scheduled Areas. The history behind enacting this law starts from the fact that the 73rd Amendment Act, itself made it clear that the provisions of the Panchayati Raj system contained in it would not apply to the scheduled areas or the tribal areas, however it provided in the same place that these provisions can be applied by way of extension to the scheduled or tribal areas mutatis mutandis, only through a Parliamentary law. Before the coming of any such law, states like Himachal Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh and Rajasthan extended the said provisions thus applying them on scheduled areas, on their own will, to which the tribal communities protested. This particular action of these states was considered unconstitutional as it violated the law laid down in the amending Act of 1992. Finally, the Andhra Pradesh High Court put the controversy to rest by declaring this extension as unconstitutional and ultra vires to it. It was thus realized after this verdict that there was a need to enact a parliamentary law if the provisions of the amending Act are to be extended to the tribal or scheduled areas. [19] Thereafter, government appointed a committee on whose recommendations a bill was introduced and ultimately the present Act saw the light of the day. The Act made it compulsory for the states having scheduled areas therein to extend the Panchayati raj provisions to those areas for which their respective Panchayati raj Acts were required to be amended. PESA provides for adequate representation of the Scheduled Tribes and tribal community in Panchayats and it also ensures that every law applied in the Fifth Scheduled areas is in consonance with their customs, beliefs and religious practices and values. Thus, the Act fortifies the right to self-determination and right to self-governance to the indigenous peoples, empowering them in consequence. Like the FRA, PESA also gives wide amplitude of powers to Gram Sabhas. PESA aims to strengthen the fundamental units of Gram Sabhas and Panchayats to grant the tribal communities the right to self-governance guaranteeing that their resources, identity and culture remain protected and well within their control. The Act is a hallmark of decentralization of governance, making grass root democracy a reality in scheduled areas.

Apart from the above discussed legislations of central level, there are other enacted laws also that deal with the protection of certain rights of tribal and scheduled tribes like the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (**Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989** and the **Protection of Civil Rights Act, 1955**. These laws protect the civil rights of the community, and attempt to shield them from the historical discrimination in the society. While the Constitution itself abolishes the practice of untouchability, it is here in the latter Act that it is made punishable also. The Acts are strict in their application providing for harsh penalties and punishments as compared to the general penal laws applicable for meting out any disrespectful behaviour towards the community.

Conclusion

Bio-cultural rights of indigenous and tribal peoples are interwoven rights which are based on an essential relation of these communities with their environment. These are inexhaustive rights which are inherent in them, thus, for their survival and well-being, these rights are inalienable. Since these communities share an intimate connection with their traditional lands, forests, language, culture, resources etc. they were highly mistaken by the world to be a threat towards the environment in which they thrive. World is witnessing that in reality, these communities are serving the role of protector, manager and conservator, in contrast to the rest of the globe who treats the ecological resources as a means to acquire wealth, thus leading to massive and irreparable exploitation of the natural resources. Since these people are highly dependent on the nature for their sustenance, any harm to the latter would necessarily imply degradation of the former. It is on this principle that the idea of bio-cultural rights sustains. Acknowledging and guaranteeing these rights, would lead betterment of not only the forest people but the forests themselves. These rights are of very wide spectrum as it inculcates every aspect of life of tribals and those who are dependent on the forests, like- right to access to biodiversity, forest produce, traditional lands and territories, indigenous or traditional knowledge, culture, language, religious or spiritual beliefs and practices. No doubt, India has progressed much since independence in the context of enacting different legislations for recognizing and protecting the indigenous people in its territory, with the Constitution holding a special place as the only constitution in the world apparently, which contains various safeguards for the tribals. The Forest Rights Act, 2006 along with the PESA, 1996 together have strengthened the fundamental units of democracy i.e. the Panchayats for the implementation of bio-cultural rights regime, but in reality, there are certain

lacunae present therein which have retarded this process. Like the FRA defines a forest dweller as a person who has resided in the forest for atleast three generations, with the word "generation" being defined herein as a period of twenty-five years. This difficult criteria of recognizing a particular forest dweller is harsh and thus it leads to exclusion of genuine cases from the purview of the Act. Further, the Gram Sabhas which have been provided additional powers by the PESA are also criticized as being controlled by the elected representatives, and are highly influenced by the national and state politics, thus, in a picture like this, the objective of welfare of local people gets faded away.[20] Additionally, practices like illegal mining also threaten the environment and the forests, making the tribal community vulnerable. The traditional knowledge of the indigenous peoples is also acquired for the exclusive use by the non-tribal people giving a huge blow to their knowledge system and heritage. As per the report of the Ministry of Tribal Affairs, only 15.5% of the total area has been recognized for the purpose of granting community forest rights, which shows a grim picture of the implementation aspect of FRA.[21] Thus, there is a need to make continuing efforts towards effective implementation of the legislations so that the indigenous community can find a respectful place in the decision-making process especially on the matters involving them or their resources, and their invaluable heritage can be protected and their rights are guaranteed.[22]

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